

PRINCIPLES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL SKILLS INSTRUMENT PERFORMANCE STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932181>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 30th March 2024

Accepted: 04th April 2024

Online: 05th April 2024

KEYWORDS

Instrument performance, musicianship, music.

ABSTRACT

The main wisdom of the development of the new Uzbekistan is to create the foundations of the 3rd Renaissance, to educate and bring up the followers of our great grandfathers who conquered the ancient world. This scientific article is written from the point of view of these urgent tasks.

ПРИНЦИПЫ И РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ ПО РАЗВИТИЮ МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ У СТУДЕНТОВ, ИГРАЮЩИХ НА ИНСТРУМЕНТАХ

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932181>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 30th March 2024

Accepted: 04th April 2024

Online: 05th April 2024

KEYWORDS

Исполнительское искусство, музыкальность, музыка.

ABSTRACT

Главная мудрость развития нового Узбекистана – создать основы III Возрождения, обучить и воспитать последователей наших прадедов, покоривших древний мир. Данная научная статья написана с точки зрения этих актуальных задач.

CHOLG'U IJROCHILIGI YO'NALISHI TALABALARIDA SOZANDALIK MAHORATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI VA TAVSIYALAR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10932181>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 30th March 2024

Accepted: 04th April 2024

Online: 05th April 2024

KEYWORDS

Cholg'u ijrochiligi, sozandalik mahorati, musiqa.

ABSTRACT

Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyotining asosiy hikmati Uchinchi Renessans poydevorini yaratish, qadim dunyoni zabt etgan alloma bobolarimizning izdoshlarini tarbiyalab voyaga yetkazishdir. Mazkur ilmiy maqola ushbu dolzarb vazifalar nuqayi nazaridan yozilgan.

Music differs from other forms of art in its means of expression, i.e. "language". The composer-student is expressed using the tones created in musical sounds, which can be perceived only by listening to the piece of music. Music is an art associated with exact time measurement. If you don't tune in to the rhythm of the music and listen to every element of it, you won't understand the piece perfectly. That's why, when you listen to music repeatedly, new artistic aspects of it increase. In the process of methodical development of musical methods in students, music lessons are organized based on the didactic theory and principles of music [1, 56]. These principles determine the main requirements and directions of the lesson content, methods and structure of the lesson. The main laws of the teaching process are clearly expressed in the didactic principles. The principles of teaching should be understood as the primary laws that define the content, methods, and forms of organization of the educational process underlying teaching and the entire process of its implementation. There is a mutual connection between the principles. Violation of one of them automatically leads to violation of the second one. From the principles come the rules of teaching. The rules determine the nature of certain methods of students of higher education institutions and lead to the implementation of principles. Rules are developed not only by didactics, but also by special methods related to the educational situation.

Principles of Consciousness and Activity. This principle is one of the leading principles of didactics. The principles of consciousness and activity of music education undergraduate students based on the teacher's leadership role in the process of teaching. and, as a result, it implies the ability to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in practice, because the acquisition of musical knowledge depends on the knowledge process, which is the main quality of the mental activity of students of the undergraduate education of music education. Conscious perception and knowledge of music, in turn, ensures that the work is kept stable in terms of artistic tone and logic. The musician-student tone learned with interest and consciously, and the tune of the music heard will remain in the memory for a lifetime.

Mastering and learning a certain piece of music by singing or listening to it artistic-aesthetic pleasure, ideological enrichment, and understanding of this work, music education undergraduate education is the priority of the student, it is necessary to be able to attract attention and arouse interest in it. Otherwise, awareness and activity will not arise. In the art of music, all types of musical activity are related to attention. Attention is especially important in public performance. In the performance, first the raised hands of the conductor, the *auttakt*, the gestures and movements between the soloist and the accompanist - all this is called "attention" in musical terminology. I. Hoffmann said, "Work is successful only when it is done with full mental concentration. However, it should be remembered that the quantitative aspect of training becomes meaningful only when combined with the qualitative aspect" [2, 93].

"The music education undergraduate course works independently because of the student's interest and desire to study. It happens due to his activeness in music lessons, diligence, and thirst for knowledge. Here, the role of the music teacher is to help the student organize his study time and teach him rational mental activity methods" [3, 19].

The principle of demonstration in music lessons. The essence of the principle of demonstrability is to create a clear, clear image for students of music education undergraduate education about the musical-theoretical subjects studied by students of higher educational

institutions and their activities. Such imaginations are the basis for a deeper understanding of the musical work. It is worth noting that visuality does not only play the role of a source of knowledge but also affects the development of students in the undergraduate course of music education. The use of visualization helps the development of thinking and speech, facilitates the transition from concrete to abstract, and helps to organize perception and attention.

The principle of demonstrability is implemented under the following conditions:

- demonstrability corresponds to the purpose and task of the lesson;
- demonstration is carried out besides verbal explanation;
- demonstration is not used excessively in the lesson;
- students correctly determine the location, time and duration of the demonstration;
- in the implementation of the demonstration, the undergraduate education of music education is based on the age characteristics and level of preparation of students.

In the course of lessons, the use of color pictures specific to the content of the works helps to clearly imagine and perceive the artistic content of the work. It is especially important to show musical sounds through the keyboard in the formation of early cognitive skills. Comprehensive use of the principle of demonstration in music education undergraduate education requires guidance and management of all aspects of students' emotional knowledge[4, 79].

In the lesson, the principle of comprehensive development and strengthening of students' knowledge levels of music education undergraduate education is one of the tasks of teaching in music education undergraduate education, which students can always apply in practice. acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies. The principles of consistency mean that music education undergraduate education should equip students with knowledge, skills, and abilities that are quickly and remembered, long-lasting, and skillfully applied in practice.

Music culture classes provide not only systematic knowledge but also provide students with a thorough mastery of the fundamentals of music education. Students of higher education institutions need to know special methods and tools that ensure this stability. For example, several types of repetition are used to form the perception of music, to ensure the solidity of mastering the knowledge gained from musical literacy, and to develop the musical abilities of students of the undergraduate education of music education.

Systematized knowledge is always carefully mastered. The strength of mastery of educational topics depends on many factors: the scientific and systematic nature of teaching, the awareness of understanding, the cognitive activity of students, the reasons for studying, and the quality of music textbooks, higher education institutions depend on the skills of the students.

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